

Plight in the Pacific: A Story from the Era of the Republic of Hawaii

by

C.J. Quion

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Approved by:

Date:

Stephen Neufeld

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Dr. Stephen Neufeld, Department of History

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Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director University Honors Program

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Brief Note from the Author:

Due to time restraints, I was not able to complete this project. I apologize to anyone who expected a full story. I especially apologize if you read all the chapters and want more after the cliffhanger. If you want to know what I had planned for this project, the main characters would have had major epiphanies. The first main character introduced would have realized that his sense of failure is a part of him and that, instead of rejecting it, should try learning from it. The second main character introduced would also realize that she is not confined to the expectations that people force upon her. The two of them would also overcome their trauma, a result of which is shown through their hyper focusing while in Honolulu. The story would have ended with the two main characters unintentionally causing the death of the antagonist through the Night Marchers, the ghosts of Native Hawaiian warriors.

Chapter 1: The Big Island

The Island of Hawai‘i, the largest and easternmost island of its home archipelago, teemed with life. Lush, green flora stretched from coast to coast. Mauna Loa towered over all island inhabitants, radiating incredible power owing to, depending on witnesses, the gods residing within or the earth churning below. In the shadows of the volcano and its dormant cousin, Mauna Kea, the inhabitants of towns and other settlements hurried about with their daily lives.

Small farmers, villages, and plantations called the more rural parts of the island their home. The few Native Hawaiian landowners tended to their taro plants for subsistence and other crops they could use to sustain a living. Village occupants, also mostly indigenous, lived in houses made of wood with thatched pili grass roofs. Plantations, owned by those of foreign ancestry, employed Chinese, Japanese, and Portuguese contract laborers to harvest sugar. These workers sweat profusely in the unforgiving heat for over half of their waking hours. They hoped to save enough money to send home or to settle in for a new life on the archipelago.

Makoa Kalili profusely sweat as he fertilized the potato field alongside Japanese workers on loan. A Native Hawaiian man from Honolulu, he worked for a small farmer and stood a head taller than most of his counterparts on the nearby plantations. His short, dark brown hair exposed his neck to the sun. He worked with a straw hat on his head, a collared button-down shirt, worn pants, and leather boots. He noticed his coworker, Shojiro Yamaguchi, approach him from the corner of his eye. Judging by the sweat on his brow Yamaguchi recently finished tending to another section of the potato field.

“What the problem?” he asked. Yamaguchi spoke unusually good English for an older Japanese man who arrived on the Big Island almost three decades ago, but still missed some conventional practices from time to time. Yamaguchi was an older, short, and stout man whose callouses demonstrated his fieldwork experiences.

“The fertilizer bags probably have rocks in them,” Makoa complained as he struggled to lift the sack.

“Here, I help,” said Yamaguchi as he rushed to his coworker’s side. After the two of them held the bag up, Makoa cut open the bag with his machete and watched the mixture spill out onto the irrigated potato field. To his surprise, he saw no rocks.

“Not what you expected, huh?” said Yamaguchi when he noticed Makoa’s bewilderment.

“I usually have no problem lifting these things,” the latter muttered loud enough for his coworker to hear.

“Maybe you getting older like me,” Yamaguchi joked. “Or maybe you just tired. It happen any day,” he followed.

“That makes sense. I didn’t sleep well last night,” said Makoa just before a nearby plantation whistle cried. Makoa and Yamaguchi used the whistle as an indicator of time, but their hired help, workers on loan from a nearby plantation, used it as a sign to return to their initial jobs.

“4:30,” Yamaguchi happily said as he pulled out a handkerchief and wiped away his sweat. “And we finish just in time too!”

“Are we heading to Mr. Naukana?” Makoa asked, referring their boss.

“Yes,” Yamaguchi replied while waving goodbye to the plantation workers who helped them today. Makoa followed suit, adjusted his straw hat, and walked with him on the dirt road that spread throughout the property. The two of them made their way down dirt roads to their employer’s residence.

“Aloha!” Mr. Simon Naukana greeted his workers. A long mustache complimented his short black and frizzled hair. He only wore clothes fitting for a property owner, such as three piece suits, on Sundays; on most days, he dressed dustily and in field clothes like his workers. Mr. Naukana inherited his land from his father, who gained it during the 1848 Mahele. He stood out on Hawai‘i Island as one of the few native landowners who lacked chiefly ancestry.

Mr. Naukana’s house fit someone of his status. He had no running water, but he enjoyed a front patio, a kitchen, a dining room, two bedrooms, and a final room that he could use for any circumstance. Glass windows dotted the painted wooden walls and allowed him to let out hot air at night.

“Come in! Grace’s making Kalua pork tonight. We picked up some rice from Hilo, too,” Mr. Naukana added. Makoa perked up at the mention of pork. This pressure-cooked delicacy reminded him of his childhood, a more innocent and less backbreaking time. His worst problem growing up as a son in the Kalili household was fearing his doting mother.

Makoa and Yamaguchi entered the dining room after removing their dust-stained boots. They saw no food on the table, but their mouths watered as they smelled the aromas entering from the kitchen. Makoa and Yamaguchi took their seats and waited eagerly for the meal. Mrs. Grace Naukana and her husband soon carried out the pork, rice, and other foods to chow down.

Mrs. Naukana, as a daughter of New England missionaries that landed on the archipelago in the 1840s, came from origins opposite her husband. She wore a white blouse with rolled-up sleeves and a long dark blue skirt that hid her leather boots. Her graying brown hair sat in a bun with a few stray strands sticking out.

“Go ahead and dig in. Elizabeth will take a while,” Mrs. Naukana said as she gestured to the food. Yamaguchi dug into the rice while Makoa swiftly impaled the kalua meat with his fork. He picked some rice and fruit as he listened to the Naukanas speak with each other.

“She’s probably reading feverishly in her room,” commented Mr. Naukana.

“Don’t act like you haven’t gotten lost in a book before,” his wife replied.

“It’s not just books for her,” Mr. Naukana retorted. “She reads a lot. She’s swallowed every dime novel you can find in Hilo. If I hadn’t known better, I’d say she can even read nonexistent words in the earth.”

“I find that criticism can be the highest praise. Are you not proud of her for taking advantage of the opportunities available these days?” Mrs. Naukana asked her husband.

“I *am* proud of her,” Mr. Naukana asserted. “I just think she could be more practical, especially since she might have to care for this place herself when we’re gone.”

“She’ll be capable when the time comes, I’m sure of that.”

“We’ll see,” replied Mr. Naukana before he continued digging into his dinner. Seconds after the two of them wrapped up their conversation, Makoa heard leather boots scurrying across the wooden floor. He saw Elizabeth, the Naukanas’ 19-year-old daughter, walk hurriedly into the dining room.

Elizabeth Pearson Naukana wore a pair of wire frame glasses. Her curly brown hair flew freely behind her as she rushed into the dining room. She wore a long-sleeved blue dress with a white collared shirt underneath. Her brown leather boots thudded as she took her seat. She greeted everyone at the table by waving awkwardly beforehand.

“What were you just reading?” Mrs. Naukana asked.

“It’s a story called “March of the Dead Johnnies.” It’s about a Marshal in Arizona fighting ghosts.”

“Ghosts?” Her dad asked bewilderedly.

“Yes!” Elizabeth said excitedly. “The ghosts in this story are the souls of Civil War soldiers on a funeral march from coast to coast. They never got the life that they thought they deserved and took it upon themselves to have a final journey. Unfortunately, everywhere they go kills the life around them, so someone needed to stop them before they reach California.”

“When I was your age,” began Mr. Naukana. “I would never have dreamed of reading that.”

“Why? Because of the ‘ungodly’ beings in it?” his daughter asked.

“No, because they weren’t sold in Hawaii at the time,” Mr. Naukana said bluntly before breaking out into laughter. In contrast, Makoa was curious about the book.

“I’ve never seen such stories, and I came from Honolulu. Where’d you find it?” Makoa spoke up. Honolulu, and O‘ahu as a whole, was a fairly cosmopolitan city at the time as a “Crossroads of the Pacific” between East Asia, the Americas, and European island holdings. Makoa thought that he would have found such a wild story back home.

“Pukui’s Books in Hilo. They happened to have one, and I took it,” Elizabeth answered, causing Makoa to raise an eyebrow.

“After paying, of course!” she added sheepishly. Everyone at the table continued sharing tidbits about what happened during the day. The plates sat stained and empty for thirty minutes after everyone finished eating.

“Anyways, I think Mr. Kalili and Mr. Yamaguchi need to rest for work tomorrow,” commented Mr. Naukana.

“We do,” responded Yamaguchi. “Thank you for the dinner, Grace,” he added, earning a smile from Mrs. Naukana.

“I enjoyed the pork, ma’am,” Makoa followed, causing Mrs. Naukana’s smile to beam brighter.

“Thank you both. We’ll see you in the field tomorrow,” she said as she waved. Makoa and Yamaguchi stood up, pushed their chairs in, and exited through the front door with a last “goodnight.” Makoa and Yamaguchi made their way by lamplight across the dark fields until they arrived at the two-room house that Makoa called a home. Their residence stood a few feet above the dirt on wooden posts. The walls, made of koa wood, kept their original vibrant brown color. A sheet metal roof kept out the rain and the sun. Mosquito nets hung where windows would have been. A curtain between Makoa and Yamaguchi’s bed gave the two men the most privacy that they could have. This was a departure from the urban splendor that Makoa enjoyed in Honolulu, but he was happy to have a roof over his head and meals to eat.

Makoa used to serve in the Hawaiian Royal Guard in Honolulu and abruptly found himself out of a job after January 1893. His mother, a Hawaiian woman of noble rank, sent him

nearby to Hawai'i Island to help him find a blank slate. She requested help from a family friend, Makoa's current boss Simon Naukana, to help her son find a change of scenery. The latter welcomed any change from Honolulu. Makoa did not hate his home city, but he found thinking of it a disruption to his current life. He knew that he would have to go back home to his family someday, but he would not worry about that until the day that it happened.

As he laid on his bed in his dust-stained clothes, Makoa propped himself up against the wall and wrote stopped sentences in his journal. *March 17, 1893: Today felt less like I'm slogging through work. Potatoes can be so taxing to grow despite being so easy. Had delicious Kālua Pork after. In all, today was better than most.* He closed his journal, satisfied with what he wrote. He soon changed into clean nightwear, washed his face, and brushed some dust off his bed. One last thought escaped his mind as he laid down and fell fast asleep.

Tonight was just one night closer to feeling better, he hoped.

Chapter 2: Mr. Hodgson Comes to Visit

Elizabeth looked outside her window at the lemon trees surrounding her family's home. She "read" the scenery as well as she read her books. The tree leaves gracefully swaying in the wind told her about the harmony of nature. The vast blue Pacific that she saw in the distance hid a larger world where she hoped to find herself. Her observations were an escape from what she thought was the boring life of a landowner's daughter. Waking up, occasional fieldwork, and the bimonthly trip to Hilo became repetitive for her years ago. She yearned for a life beyond this, but in a way that respected her parents' role in her life. *Writing might be the best way to go about it*, she pondered to herself. Elizabeth heard the door knock and saw her father enter, snapping her out of her thoughts.

"Eliza, your neighbor and I are negotiating a price for a portion of the land," he announced. "Come join us. It will teach you lessons in reasoning with others for when the time comes." Mr. Naukana had a habit of giving his life lessons to her whether she wanted to hear it or not. Once, a simple trip to Hilo to sell potatoes quickly turned into a 3-hour lecture on morality, her ancestors, and basic dating advice. Elizabeth wondered what the discussion would spur into, so she showed some interest in attending the meeting with Mr. Hodgson.

"Sure, dad. I'll come along," she replied half-enthusiastically. Her dad did not seem to notice as he smiled and left. Elizabeth tied her boots on, brushed the dust off her dress, and made her way to the dining room.

“And this is my daughter, Elizabeth,” her father announced proudly. Elizabeth picked up the skirt of her dress and bowed.

“A pleasure,” Mr. George Hodgson nodded in response as he sat at the dinner table with Mr. and Mrs. Naukana. He wore a handsome three-piece black suit and a black bowler hat sat on the table in front of him. His beard, trimmed and respectable for a man of his standing, had patches of gray that showed the pressures of his life as a former settler on the US frontier.

“I wanted to thank you again for lending some workers again during this planting season.”

“Not a problem,” started Mr. Hodgson. “Most of the ones I send you are newcomers, so your men are teaching them the trade so that mine can be concerned with other business.”

“Again, I am grateful. What brings you to seek audience with us today?” asked Mr. Naukana. Elizabeth turned curiously toward the guest.

“We discussed the possibility that I could purchase some unused land. You mentioned as its owner that-”

“We are caretakers of the land,” stressed Mr. Naukana. “Sure, I legally own it. But I do not like to say we own it, as it is our family.” Elizabeth thought about her father’s words because of how much emphasis he put on being a caretaker rather than an owner. He taught her at a young age that the land was her family and that she should care for it as such. She knew of stories involving the Earth mother Papahānaumoku, but in practical terms the land also gave all living beings what they needed to live.

“Caretakers. Alright, I see it,” Mr. Hodgson responded. “Before I consider any purchases, I would like to ask some questions.”

“Go on,” said Mrs. Naukana. Mr. Hodgson raised an eyebrow.

“I should mention that my wife has as much a say in this decision as I do. She does as much work for us here as everyone else does, if not more,” commented Elizabeth’s father.

“Ah, I see. When I was settling in Wyoming, that was very much my experience too. I saw women farming, running shops, shooting, even voting! I had not been accustomed to seeing it here,” responded Mr. Hodgson. Elizabeth daydreamed. She knew of powerful women in Hawaiian history. Queen Ka‘ahumanu helped abolish the restrictive Kapu System. Governess Ke‘elikolani of Hawai‘i Island reportedly halted the advances of Mauna Loa lava in 1881 by making offerings to Pele. Perhaps the women in this “waio-min” were an entire population of women as capable as the Hawaiian chiefesses.

“What problems have you dealt with as caretakers of the land?” Mr. Hodgson asked, snapping Elizabeth back to reality.

“We’ve had no problems other than the occasional rat infestation. This land has good access to water and a diverse crop population to prevent the spread of disease.”

“What crops do you grow? I see lemon trees, a small patch of taro,” Mr. Hodgson recalled. “Am I missing others?”

“Lemon trees, taro, Kahalu‘u trees, potatoes, I could go on,” Elizabeth’s mother chimed in enthusiastically. “Our irrigation system blesses us with the ability to grow those.” Mr. Hodgson gave a slight smile to the answer.

“Is there anything else I should know about the land?”

“Other than the fact that we care for it, no,” joked Mr. Naukana, earning a laugh from Mr. Hodgson.

“And you are willing to part with 20 acres of your land?”

“That’s what I said, yes,” affirmed Elizabeth’s father.

“Name your price per acre. I have plans for new infrastructure to benefit my operations and your land would be beneficial to me.”

“I have no price right now, but do come back in a week and I shall have a price for you,” Mr. Naukana responded. Elizabeth thought that this was a good decision. The deal could easily have spurred into an impulsive “in the moment” purchase had her father not gone that route.

“Come on, surely there’s a price that’s been on your mind. \$500 an acre? \$550?” Mr. Hodgson egged on his neighbor. Mr. Naukana barely held on to his right to vote in 1887 with his 43 acre property valued at \$3022, or so Elizabeth recalled. Mr. Hodgson naming his price near five times the amount of each acre was worth certainly prompted his neighbor to reconsider, since Elizabeth saw her parents eye each other in unspoken conversation.

“My earlier statement still stands. Come back next week and I will have a price for you,” Mr. Naukana resisted.

“\$600 per acre, and I will pay all the transfer and paperwork fees,” said Mr. Hodgson as he flashed his neighbors an ambitious smile.

“I will tell you next week,” Elizabeth heard her father sound more irritated at Mr. Hodgson’s insistence.

“But it could be now before someone else gives you a lower price per acre.”

“Better any price well-thought than a commitment to money that I don’t see,” Mr. Naukana retorted.

“I beg your pardon?” Mr. Hodgson asked. Elizabeth watched intently as the dialogue came to a standstill.

“I know what’s been happening at your plantation. At least a dozen of your workers tried running off and seeking employment elsewhere despite their contracts and the consequences of breaking them. Some of your laborers speak of your harsh plantation police and enjoy it much better here, where they have the same work but much more happiness. Do you think I want to give an impulsive price to a business with discontent workers?” Mr. Naukana asked.

“The Hodgson Hawaii Sugar Company can only spend money to make more money,” the sugar baron tried to reassure his client to no avail. Elizabeth read her father’s eyes; judging by the frown on his face, he would have rolled them had he not wanted to keep polite company.

“You will have a price next week,” Mr. Naukana bluntly stated, his patience worn thin.

“Think about your daughter: if either of you suddenly pass away, she won’t know how to tend to the land, but she will know how to manage a generous sum of money. Money tends to speak better than any language these days. Whoever receives it from her would be very willing to look past her... mongrel status,” Mr. Hodgson reasoned.

Mongrel. Elizabeth fumed at such language. The word paid no homage to the benefits of her bicultural upbringing and, with the way Mr. Hodgson uttered that word, he did not intend to honor himself either.

“Get out,” Mrs. Naukana said calmly.

“I beg your pardon?”

“You may leave. Talking about our daughter like that is not welcome in this household,”

Mr. Naukana added.

“But I still would like to buy-”

“And I was willing to sell. I let you in because I thought you could respond to my business concerns and reassure me that I was making a worthy investment. You could not even pay the cost of basic decency, so you are free to leave,” Elizabeth’s father said coldly. Mr. Hodgson quickly turned to Mrs. Naukana.

“Grace?” He addressed her by her first name as a last-ditch effort.

“I let you know how I felt about your words. Please let us be for now,” she responded.

“As you wish,” Mr. Hodgson finally gave up.

“Makoa, would you be so kind as to show our guest the way out?” Mrs. Naukana asked. Elizabeth saw Mr. Hodgson sullenly stand up and walk out of the room with Makoa in tow. She noticed that her father leaned in close to her.

“I’m sorry you had to see that. Your mother and I both expected him to have some patience, but sometimes who we think someone is and who someone actually is, are two completely different things,” he said. Mrs. Naukana sat at the table opposite her husband.

“I knew George and his parents,” she started sadly. “They were some of the kindest people I knew. I thought that the corruption of their family name by his brother would have ended after his death, but it looks like he passed on his greed to another.”

“People change, don’t they? In the same way where characters in stories change for the better, sometimes they change for the worse,” Elizabeth pointed out.

“She would not have learned that without reading,” her mother reminded her husband to lighten the mood. Mr. Naukana let out a half-hearted chuckle.

“I need to think of what we’ll do next. Mr. Hodgson will surely withdraw his labor and leave Makoa and Yamaguchi as my only workers. The five of us are not enough to work 43 acres,” he commented.

“How long will it take us to find more workers?” asked Elizabeth.

“Two weeks. I will spend a few days Hilo to meet some contacts. They might help,” said Mr. Naukana. “In the meantime, everyone needs to help take care of the land in most of their waking hours.”

“Will we have a house meeting with Mr. Kalili and Mr. Yamaguchi about this?” Elizabeth asked.

“Yes, we will meet later. For now, we should rest. Your mother and I have an idea of the journey that lies ahead.”

Chapter 3: In the Bay and On the Land

Makoa waited impatiently as he and Yamaguchi fished in Hilo Bay. Straw hats protected their heads from the relentless sun as they used their fishing poles. The water peacefully sat below their rowboat. Technicolor fish swam rhythmically across coral reefs, making moving rainbows beneath the bay. The Pacific that lay far beyond hid wonders and terrors that Makoa could think of during another time. For now, he needed to focus on the frustration of making a catch.

“You never fish before?” Yamaguchi asked.

“I haven’t.”

“Then why come along?”

“I wanted to learn something today that wasn’t related to caring for the land,” responded Makoa.

“Hmph. First rule of fishing: everyone must have patience,” Yamaguchi said matter of factly.

“That’s philosophical,” Makoa said dryly. “Some teaching from Nihon?”

“No, life experience from almost thirty years on these islands,” Yamaguchi started as he put his rod down, turned to Makoa, and locked eyes with him. “Why do you mention my homeland?”

“I didn’t mean anything by it,” Makoa quickly defended himself.

“Not mad, just curious. You try to steer me towards Nihon from time to time, but always stop short of asking a question.”

“You don’t have to tell me anything, Mr. Yamaguchi,” Makoa said unconvincingly. He felt Yamaguchi’s eyes bore into his soul as some silence passed. “I guess the truth is that I’m dealing with anger towards my past failures and my focus on you is a distraction from myself.”

“Ah, so you are failure.”

“Yes!” Makoa suddenly agreed. “I mean: I know that thinking that way isn’t healthy.”

“No need to explain. I am no stranger to this feeling.” Yamaguchi said.

“Huh?”

“I keep it short: before I arrived here, I was a Ronin.”

“Ronin?”

“A wandering bandit. I robbed travelers,” Yamaguchi answered while disgusted at himself. “I caused too much trouble for police one day, so I went to port to find a ship to take me far away. A foreigner told me to sign contract and they put me with many other Nihonjin. We come to Hawaii and they work us like dogs.”

“So that’s how you got here? To get away from the police?” Makoa asked.

“Yes, but my focus is not the police. I bring up plantation because I learn who I am there. I worked long hours in the heat with the danger of the plantation managers and wasps looming over me. It was miserable, but it was an honest living compared to home. I learned to work with

what I have. I learn better English too, which helped me when I stayed here after my contract finished. I had nowhere back in Nihon since my family disowned me for resorting to crime and dishonoring their name.”

“What do I do with all this information? You’ve told me more about yourself in five minutes than the last two years!”

“Makoa-san, I try to show you that I thought I was failure too.”

“That’s nothing compared to losing your destiny to foreigners,” Makoa said bitterly.

“Would you like to tell me of this ‘destiny?’”

“Another time,” Makoa said. He saw Yamaguchi put his hands up and slowly turn around to resume his fishing.

“It’s just... “I was given the opportunity to serve in the Royal Guard thanks to my mother,” he started, catching his fishing partner’s attention again. The Hawaii Royal Guard was a modern protective force boasting European-style military uniforms, powerful artillery, and prestige last seen afforded to the protectors of Kamehameha I. “She saw that I stood up for my peers in school and thought that I could put it to use serving the monarchy. When American soldiers landed in Honolulu in January 1893, I was paralyzed. I wanted to fight back, but the Queen made it clear that she wanted no violence that day. Before I know it,” Makoa trailed off, paining him to think of the memory. “Those who acted against the Queen dissolved the guard and everything I learned over the years meant nothing.”

“I know what it’s like to lose purpose, Makoa-san.”

“You don’t,” Makoa said coldly. He quickly realized how harshly he acted toward Yamaguchi. He covered his face in shame. “I’m sorry. I’ve been so stressed out about our work that it’s worsened the way I’ve felt about myself.”

“It’s not just the stress. I admit that our circumstances are not the same and I am foolish to make it appear as so, but what we have in common is our journey. You have just started yours and I continue on mine.”

“What journey?”

“One towards betterment. How has your life changed since your arrival?”

“No running water,” Makoa said bluntly, causing Yamaguchi to laugh.

“For the better!” the latter said amusedly.

“I can journal and sit on the roof of our home and watch the sunset,” Makoa responded.

“And you have done this every day?”

“Yes, even after losing our help.”

“So you are not a failure that way.”

“I guess. But that doesn’t change that I’m out of a job because I failed to protect Hawai‘i.”

“Time heals plenty of wounds, Makoa-san. Give yourself more time and see what happens,” Yamaguchi advised.

“Easier said than done,” Makoa said as he concentrated on his fishing rod again.

“Most certainly,” replied Yamaguchi. “Perhaps we should focus on the fish now, then head to Hilo with our catches?”

“Yeah,” affirmed Makoa. The two of them went silent as they focused on fishing. Yamaguchi’s ideas bounced around in Makoa’s head, needing some time before they materialized in a way that he understood.

As the sun set over Hawai‘i Island, Mr. Hodgson watched as his plantation police walked around the plantation houses. Calling them houses was too kind. Said structures were long, wooden barracks where his workers slept with mats, mosquito nets, and almost no privacy. He could afford to give them better benefits, but his workers feared complaining and Mr. Hodgson had the goal of his workers surviving, not being comfortable. Comfortable workers could happen when he found a business model that worked reliably for his operations. He needed to make sacrifices and take some losses to get there. He wanted to make his plantation a machine with organic components. *Everything must be efficient*, he said to himself from time to time.

Every move was a business decision to Mr. Hodgson, but he did not care for the money. The meaning behind money meant more to him, as he could use it to show others that his business failures on the mainland were only temporary obstacles that led towards his destiny as one of the most powerful sugar planters on the Hawaiian Islands. To ensure that his workers’ discontent would not drive down his production, Mr. Hodgson hired a private police force to maintain order and quell discontent. He found this stability more important because of his experiences on the mainland. The nearest sheriff was miles away out on the frontier, and having personal police to protect him and his business gave him the closure that he could not find then.

“Bedtime! Bedtime! Get your rest,” the head policeman loudly shouted a final time before he reported back to Mr. Hodgson.

“Looks like they’re all asleep, sir,” said Edgar Dalton. He was a graying, well-built man who wore a dust-stained white shirt, blue pants, and a flat cap. Company laborers easily distinguished plantation police from their supervisors through the former two articles of clothing and a club in hand.

“Very good, Dalton. I take that there wasn’t any trouble with them today?”

“Bradley got hit by one of the Japanese, sir,” Dalton responded.

“This is the third incident within the past week. Why’s this happening?”

“If I may, sir: all the men who attacked mine were newcomers who worked for the Naukanas. Maybe they’re angry that they don’t get to work for them anymore.”

“They never worked for *them*,” Mr. Hodgson started with vitriol. “They’ve always worked for *me*. They have a *contract* with me. I never should’ve let them be anywhere outside of my operations.”

“What do we do about the workers, sir?”

“If fights continue, cut all their wages,” Mr. Hodgson said without a second thought.

“And what about the Naukanas?”

“Simon’s been a thorn in my side for his stubbornness. The sheriff’s on my payroll. We move tomorrow night.”

“Yes, sir,” Dalton said.

Chapter 4: Deal with a Devil

Elizabeth woke up to the sound of one of her windows shattering. She screamed as more glass burst apart and landed before her bed. She heard men trampling and shouting outside. Lanterns burned around the residence and gave a hellish glow to the Naukana land. The shadows that hit the invaders’ faces gave them the appearance of sunken pitch-black eyes made more threatening by their weapons and aggressive demeanor.

“Don’t touch my daughter!” she heard her father shout as she watched an unfamiliar man burst into her room, a scowl on his face illuminated by lantern light. His calloused hands held a wooden club that saw much use against plantation workers. He slowly approached Elizabeth as she huddled against her bedroom wall with her arms out for protection.

“Get the hell up,” he said as his advance came to a still. Elizabeth still felt herself paralyzed with fear.

“I’m not laying a hand on you, but I will if you don’t do what I say,” the man said as he beat his club against his palm. “Now, get up.”

Still in her nightwear, Elizabeth quickly slid her boots on before the man led her to the front porch of her family’s home. She saw her parents, Mr. Kalili, and Mr. Yamaguchi kneeling or sitting in the center of a group of more rough-looking men.

“Now sit here, be quiet, don’t move, and nothing bad will happen to you,” said her captor as he stepped back and stood guard in the residence doorway. Elizabeth did as he asked since she

had no better alternative. She took the time to look closer at everyone she knew outside. It soon dawned on her that she might have been the luckiest one.

Her father first caught her eye. He wore his sleepwear with dust caking the white fabrics. One of his captors tied a handkerchief around his mouth, silencing him except for a few panicked breaths, and bound his arms too. He knelt as two men loomed over him like vultures waiting for their prey to die. Elizabeth's mother sat further back from her husband. She also wore her nightwear and was untouched for the most part. Most of the men kept their backs turned towards her, but they bounded her arms and legs. When she turned around to peek at Elizabeth, the latter noticed tears streaming down her face.

Mr. Kalili sat further from her parents and away from Elizabeth. He still wore his sweaty and dusty field clothes as three guards around him. He scowled at them occasionally, and Elizabeth caught him muttering under his breath after he did so. The men also tied his arms and legs together but left him untouched compared to his coworker. Mr. Yamaguchi took the worst of the violence that happened that night. He lacked a shirt as blood dripped out of his nose and onto the soil. The men tied his arms and legs and forced him to sit on his knees. If he faltered, one of his guards hit him with the palm of his hand and taunted him to stay up. Said guard took sadistic joy as he demeaned Mr. Yamaguchi with ethnic slurs and taunts. After a tense few minutes, Mr. Hodgson emerged from a new crowd of men that arrived on the land.

“George, you sadist! Wait till Sheriff Kenui finds out about this!” Elizabeth's mother shouted in rage.

“Sheriff Kenui won’t care about a little property seizure. The money that I gave him is enough. Money that would’ve gone to you if you and your husband just accepted my generous offer,” Mr. Hodgson said nonchalantly.

“Don’t talk to Mrs. Naukana like that, sir,” Makoa asked, thinly concealing his scorn for Mr. Hodgson.

“Quiet,” Mr. Hodgson responded with the tone. “Silence him. I’m in the middle of something here.” One man quickly wrapped a handkerchief around Mr. Kalili’s mouth. Mr. Hodgson then approached Elizabeth’s father.

“Hold him up and let him speak,” the former said to the two guards. The men quickly hoisted Mr. Naukana as one of them yanked off the saliva-heavy handkerchief. Elizabeth saw her father stand stoically inches in front of Mr. Hodgson.

“You sick bastard,” Mr. Naukana said as he panted heavily.

“Call me what you want, but this is your destiny as it is mine,” Mr. Hodgson said matter-of-factly.

“What kind of destiny requires you to covet thy neighbors’ goods?” asked Elizabeth’s father, invoking the scriptures to reason with his captor.

“The Bible cannot protect you from Indian violence, or business failures, or whatever life throws at you. What’s happening now is no different. If you don’t die tonight, you can only emerge a stronger man or be shattered and forgotten,” Mr. Hodgson said. Elizabeth was shocked at how casually he treated the whole matter, as though he spent every day taking families hostage and deflecting their emotional responses.

“Don’t die tonight?” Mrs. Naukana interjected.

“My men and I aren’t interested in taking any lives tonight, but we’ll be happy to make any arrangements if so,” Mr. Hodgson stated.

“You’re a monster!” Elizabeth suddenly shouted, outraged by how Mr. Hodgson treated them all. She quickly cupped her hands over her mouth as she felt all the attention focus on her.

“I told you not to say anything!” said her guard as he leaned in front of her with his club.

“Ah, Mr. Dalton. Would you be so kind as to show everyone here what happens when someone interrupts me again?” asked Mr. Hodgson.

“I don’t want to hit a young woman, sir,” Elizabeth heard her guard say.

“And I didn’t want the sale of land to resort to this, but we can’t all have what we want. So show everyone what will happen if someone interrupts me again.”

“Yes, sir,” said Mr. Dalton. Elizabeth noticed several men looked at her and her guard uneasily as the latter quickly winded up his club. She screamed as she suddenly felt a blunt pain in her arm above the elbow. While she tried recovering from the pain, she saw Mr. Hodgson’s men restrain her father from breaking free.

“No bones broken that time; you should be thankful,” noted the sugar baron. Everyone stayed silent.

“Nothing to say after earlier? Good. So here’s what happens next,” Mr. Hodgson started, addressing both of Elizabeth’s parents. “I give you a contract for the sale of all 43 acres of your land, you both sign it, I give you the money arranged in the agreement, and then you’ll go to some nearby village and not interfere with my business again.”

Mr. Hodgson did not even wait for a response as he beckoned two men forward. One held a quill and ink while the other had the contract.

“This isn’t binding. We’re under duress,” Mrs. Naukana pointed out.

“The law means nothing when you can’t enforce it,” Mr. Hodgson responded. Elizabeth saw the men step forward, pressuring her parents into signing the contract. The latter two looked at each other reluctantly, trying to think of some miraculous way to escape their current predicament. Elizabeth’s mother was the first to pick up a quill. Her hand trembled as she dipped the tip of the feather in the pot of ink and signed the document. Her husband followed suit.

“Such beautiful calligraphy after all that happened tonight. Looks like you all may emerge from this stronger than before,” Mr. Hodgson said with a smile. “As per our agreement, you will gather your belongings and my men will take you to the edge of my land. They’ll give you money and let you leave,” Mr. Hodgson started. “Let them go but watch them closely. Keep the two workers here,” he commanded. Elizabeth rubbed her arm as the men untied her parents and forced them towards the porch. Her father got close and pulled her along with him.

“Only take what you mind losing. We can’t guarantee that everything will be here when we get back,” Elizabeth’s father said in a hushed voice. Elizabeth quickly made her way to her bedroom and looked around. She had plenty of books and clothes that she wished to keep but only enough space for a handful. Two books, three dresses, and two sets of nightwear went into her bag as Elizabeth changed into a new dress and put her boots back on. While she tied her laces, she felt her stress catch up as several tears fell from her eyes.

“Stop him!” Elizabeth heard someone shout. She wiped them away quickly as she dashed out of the room with her knapsack to find the commotion. Upon arriving at the porch, Elizabeth

saw several of Mr. Hodgson's men punching and kicking Mr. Yamaguchi as he held his unbound hands to his face. She saw two men restrain him as he coughed up blood while the rest stepped away on orders of Mr. Hodgson.

"What's the meaning of this?" the sugar baron asked.

"He spit in my direction, sir," said the guard who kept hitting Mr. Yamaguchi earlier.

"After you spent all this time demeaning me like I am nothing," Mr. Yamaguchi growled.

"Shut up!" the guard shouted back before he moved to hit his prisoner again. Elizabeth watched in horror as the club slammed into the side of Mr. Yamaguchi's head, knocking him out cold.

"No!" Elizabeth heard her father cry as he rushed forward. Two of Mr. Hodgson's men quickly blocked his way and shoved him to the ground.

"This is just business as usual in our operations," Mr. Hodgson responded. "Good thing you won't have to witness this anymore after tonight."

"No wonder your workers complained to me," Elizabeth's father said defiantly.

"It's all just practical business, Simon. Just like I encouraged you to sell me your land, my police and I encourage my workers to be productive," the sugar baron corrected him.

"Wait till your friends in Honolulu hear about what you did tonight!" shouted Elizabeth's mother, causing Mr. Hodgson to laugh darkly.

"Big dreams for small farmers. I will say nothing else. Men, take these people off my property," he replied coldly.

Fireflies hovered in the night sky of Wainuku village. Its native inhabitants, relatives of Elizabeth through her father's side, came out to observe the new arrivals. The atmosphere of excitement quickly died down when they saw the sorry state of the Naukanas and their two workers. Upon seeing Mr. Yamaguchi with dried blood on his skin, some of them gasped and rushed to his aid when he fell to his knees. As said villagers helped Mr. Yamaguchi up, an older woman approached Mr. Naukana. Her silver hair glistened in the moonlight and her weathered face frowned.

"Simon! How dare you..." her husky voice trailed off when she saw the scene before her.

"Miriam, I'll introduce everyone later, but we need shelter," said Mr. Naukana wearily.

"Do you have any to spare?"

"Y- You all can sleep in my living room," the woman started apprehensively. "I just need help pushing some things aside. I have mats you can sleep on."

"That's more than I hoped for. Thank you, Miriam," Mr. Naukana said gratefully. He turned to Elizabeth.

"Eliza, this is my sister, your Aunt Miriam. You haven't met her before because we disagreed over my marriage to your mother."

"We can talk about that later after all this is sorted out. I'm even more upset that you've kept me from my niece!"

"You will get to know her while we stay with you for now," responded Mr. Naukana.

"Follow your aunt. She'll show you where we're staying."

Aunt Miriam gestured to follow her as she trekked towards her home. Elizabeth followed with Mr. Kalili in tow. Her parents stayed behind to help Mr. Yamaguchi and grab their baggage. When Elizabeth finally arrived at the house, she saw it wasn't much different from where she lived. The wooden walls possessed no glass windows. The only difference was that the roof was made of thatched grass. When she entered, she saw a modest living room that had some parlor chairs, a table, and a lantern in the center.

"You two help me move this," Aunt Miriam said. She went to another room while Elizabeth and Mr. Kalili pushed the chairs to the corners. When Elizabeth's aunt returned, she had two rolls of woven mats.

"Lay these out. I'll get three more and pillows," she added. Once they finished refurbishing the living room, Aunt Miriam made her way to the front door.

"I'm sorry that I couldn't get you more," she said sadly.

"We'll be alright; we just need rest," replied Elizabeth. Aunt Miriam nodded and exited the house.

"I need to lay down," said Mr. Kalili as he lay on his mat exhausted. Elizabeth soon heard him snore as she gently placed her knapsack to the side. She took her mat while she listened to her parents and Aunt Miriam talking outside on the porch.

The tears stopped earlier as Elizabeth focused on the journey to Wainuku, but after she sat on her mat and put her sack away, she looked at her bruised arm. The stress of her current situation caught up again. She had wanted to be free of the confines of her home, but not through losing it.

I should've been careful about what I wished for, she said to herself quietly.

Chapter 5: Stepping Stones

Everything happened so quickly for Makoa. Being rudely woken up in the middle of the night. Being held hostage by landgrabbers. Watching his coworker take blows that almost killed him. Losing his livelihood and items in minutes. Taking refuge in a village where he needed to share a room with his employers. The last situation certainly beat sleeping on the ground while exposed to the elements. Still, last night disrupted what he thought was his life getting better. As he stared at the ceiling, he relived through the previous hours just as he spent nights reliving that fateful night in Honolulu.

“Mr. Kalili?” Makoa heard someone say. He snapped out of his trance and looked to his right. He saw Elizabeth looking at him from her sleeping mat.

“Are you okay, Mr. Kalili?”

“I’m fine,” Makoa responded.

“I was reading your eyes.”

“Don’t you mean ‘looking at?’”

“No, reading. Like a book. I see things other people have trouble seeing, and it’s very similar to reading.”

“Alright, ‘reading,’” Makoa said in disbelief. He was more focused on recovering from the previous night than trying to understand something new about his employer’s daughter. He looked at Yamaguchi, who slept soundly on a mat. Despite his condition, he slept peacefully.

“Do you think he’ll be okay?” Elizabeth asked.

“He told me that he’s survived many things,” Makoa began. “If he’s telling the truth, this won’t be an exception.” He and Elizabeth saw Mrs. Naukana enter the room.

“Miriam and I made breakfast,” she quietly said as she gestured to the kitchen. “Some eggs and potatoes whenever you’re ready.”

“Thanks, mom,” responded Elizabeth.

“Yeah, thanks,” Makoa followed suit. The two grabbed their hot breakfasts and chowed away while they sat on their host’s porch. Mr. and Mrs. Naukana soon joined them with their own plates while the former brandished a piece of paper underneath his.

“Before we left our home, I took the time to grab a letter written by our attorney in Honolulu,” Mr. Naukana began, causing Elizabeth to look up from her food.

“Why a letter? Don’t you carry around his contact information?” she asked.

“I have not called on him too many times, but I can always count on him when I do. The only issue is that he wrote to me that he was going into hiding because the government wants him for his dissenting views. He gave me a poem that I could use to find him and it makes no sense. Take a look,” said Mr. Naukana. Makoa and Elizabeth both hovered over the paper he gave them.

Dear Simon,

I'm hidden I'm hidden for my perspectives

Because I opposed the govt's directives

I no longer can help your legal woes

Or problems with a thorny rose

I will make just one thing clear

If you happen to need me near

In Honolulu I am safe

Yes safely hidden in this place

Where juice makes fights between men and boys

The Shining Moon brings Joy.

Regards,

Asher Kawainui, Attorney at Law

“I’m impressed,” commented Makoa.

“Seconded,” Elizabeth added.

“As was I, but he only gave me this letter and I cannot think of what he’s talking about for the life of me.”

“So you want us to head to Honolulu to find him?” Makoa asked.

“It’s our only hope. If he cannot make his arguments in court, he can at least find someone to make his arguments. If Mr. Hodgson wanted to use force, then we can helpfully remind him that we at least respect the law here.”

“When do we leave?” Elizabeth asked as her voice quivered both from excitement and nervousness.

“As soon as Mr. Kalili gets new clothes,” Mr. Naukana said, causing Makoa to look down at his dusty attire, unchanged from last night. Mr. Naukana went on. “I put aside money for two tickets on an interisland steamer that departs from Hilo daily.”

“Wait, just her and I?” Makoa asked.

“We’d go too, but Mr. Yamaguchi needs some help with his wounds. He knows no one else here, so we will be here with him,” replied Mrs. Naukana.

“I’m surprised that you’re both letting me go with Mr. Kalili,” Elizabeth commented. Makoa saw Mr. and Mrs. Naukana eye each other silently.

“Your mother and I were hesitant, but since we can’t leave, we’re sending you as our representative. Besides, I’ve known Mr. Kalili’s family for decades. I can trust him with you,” answered Mr. Naukana.

“I’ll keep her safe, sir,” Makoa nodded.

“Good. The steamer leaves at 3 PM. One of Aunt Miriam’s neighbors is heading to Hilo to deliver some garments and he’ll let you ride on his wagon. Once you’re there, prepare the best you can for the trip and hop on the boat. After that, do what you need to get in contact with Mr. Kawainui.”

“We can do it, dad,” Elizabeth spoke up. Makoa saw him return the nervous smile of a worried parent, the same one his own mother gave him before he left for Hawai‘i Island.

“I trust you both,” he started. “Now, go.” After that, Makoa and Elizabeth collected the money and bags that they needed to spend time in Hilo. They then hopped on the wagon departing the village following anxious goodbyes from Elizabeth to her parents. In the distance, a man watched through his binoculars as he wore a familiar white shirt and blue pants as a club hung at his side.

“The boss won’t be happy to hear of this,” he commented to himself as he made his way back to the Hodgson plantation.

Honolulu, the capital of the Hawaiian Islands, was part of a vast economic network that connected Asia, the Americas, and the rest of the Pacific. At the time of the conquests of King Kamehameha I at the turn of the 19th century, foreign ships anchored further off the coast to trade with the natives. When the conqueror seized O‘ahu after a bloody battle, one that resulted in its last defenders leaping off the cliffs of Nu‘uanu Pali, he gained control of the only natural harbor in the archipelago. His son, Kamehameha III, began initiatives that further developed Honolulu into a trade center and rest stop for travelers of the Pacific.

Elizabeth saw the effects of that vast economic network clearly. As she and Makoa walked the boulevards, she saw all sights that she could only dream of being in Hilo. Japanese family-owned shops and American department stores operated around the city. Streetcars ferried people from place to place, a technology she had only seen in the newspapers. A few factories stood in the distance as part of recent ambitions to bring more industry to the islands.

“You’ve been around this all your life?” Elizabeth asked in awe.

“You can gawk at everything later. We need to find Mr. Kawainui right now,” Makoa said abruptly.

“Why so sour? You came from here, didn’t you?”

“And I left,” groaned Makoa. “I’d rather not be here, but your father needs us to help him.”

“Alright, Mr. Kalili,” affirmed Elizabeth.

“And you don’t have to call me Mr. Kalili. ‘Makoa’ is fine. I’m not that much older than you, anyway.”

“Huh?”

“I’m 23,” Makoa said bluntly.

“I just realized how little I know about you despite the fact that you worked for my dad for two years. There’s so much to tell each other! You’re like a new book that I can’t wait to read,” Elizabeth said enthusiastically.

“This is going to be a long trip,” her fellow traveler sighed. The two of them traveled up and down the roads of Honolulu until they reached a manor far too familiar to Makoa. A black tile roof protected its inhabitants from the elements. A balcony, held up by gray stone columns, wrapped around its second floor while it held empty tables and rocking chairs. Its walls, made of lava rocks carved into bricks and plastered together, featured several glass windows that cloth canopies hung over. Gardens and shrubbery encased in a metal fence also surrounded the manor.

“I didn’t tell her that I was coming, so don’t be surprised if we have to stay somewhere else,” Makoa commented as he saw Elizabeth gazing at the home in wonder.

“Who are we meeting?” she asked while not taking her eyes off the building.

“You’ll find out soon enough,” Makoa said as he opened the gate and strolled onto the property. He heard Elizabeth follow suit as she closed the gate behind her. He froze when he got to the set of double doors at the front of the house. His companion stood behind him quietly for a few seconds before speaking up.

“Do you want me to knock?” she asked, breaking him out of his trance.

“I got it,” he mumbled as he delivered three strong knocks against the doors.

“Hello, I’m afraid...” a butler began as he opened the door. He immediately stopped when he saw Makoa standing on the porch.

“Just a moment, please,” the man asked politely as he quickly shut the door. The new arrivals heard muffled footsteps and shouting as a minute passed by. When the door opened again, Makoa found himself face-to-face with his mother.

Abigail Kalili had strong features and experiences that made her well-respected among Hawaiian nobility. Her dark brown eyes blazed with an intensity that reflected her outspoken nature. Her prim and proper posture never wavered. Even the way that she dressed made a statement; whether she was in a night dress receiving visitors or attending an elegant dinner, she understood what to wear to reflect herself without drawing too much attention. She received her education from the missionary-founded O’ahu College, the institution that later became Punahou

School. Mrs. Kalili only showed her intensity when she suddenly saw her son standing at the door, immediately wrapping her arms around her son as he could only accept his situation.

“And who’s your friend?” Makoa’s mother asked.

“Mom, this is Elizabeth. She’s Mr. Naukana’s daughter. Elizabeth, this my mother,” Makoa said begrudgingly. He watched as his companion waved politely.

“Simon’s mentioned his daughter, but I haven’t had the pleasure to meet her until now,” Mrs. Kalili began. “Oh, what are we doing still standing here? Come in! We just had the parlor cleaned!”

“Mom, I need to mention: we’re not looking to partake in any events while we’re here. Mr. Naukana’s in trouble. A sugar baron forced him to sign away his land under force and we need to find his lawyer so we can reverse everything,” Makoa said. His mother slowly returned to the personality that those outside the family knew her for: that of a prim, proper, and outspoken lady.

“I see. I regret that we meet under these circumstances,” she lamented. “How may I help?”

“Elizabeth and I also need a place to stay while we’re here. I thought it would be better to come to you.”

“You made the right choice, dear. Of course, you’ll both be safe,” Mrs. Kalili responded warmly, her persona melting away again.

“Thanks, mom,” Makoa said, easing into being comfortable in Honolulu in spite of everything that happened.

“I am happy to have you here. Joseph will show you to your rooms. When will you go out and find Simon’s attorney?”

“If I may, ma’am,” Elizabeth started. “Makoa and I decided that tomorrow morning would be the best time. I think he suggested 8 AM?” she finished. Her companion nodded.

“I’ll keep that in mind. Go on and follow Joseph. We’ll have much to talk about over dinner tonight,” said Mrs. Kalili with a smile. Makoa and Elizabeth followed the butler to their rooms on the upper floor while their host regained her composure. She sat in the parlor for a few minutes before she heard the front doors knock again. Another butler came into the room.

“The one that you just sent for is here now, ma’am,” he said. “I’ve left him at the door.”

“Good. I won’t keep him waiting,” she responded. Mrs. Kalili walked out, opened the door, and faced a new visitor who wore a white shirt and blue pants.

“I got your message a few minutes ago. He just met you?” the man asked.

“Yes, let your boss know that my son’s arrived,” Mrs. Kalili replied. “I wouldn’t suggest moving on him just yet. Wait till he’s settled in.”